

DEVELOPING THE READING LEVEL OF GRADE THREE NON-READERS THROUGH PROJECT GRP (Guided Reading Procedure)

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ABSTRACT

The study dealt with the developing of the reading level of Grade Three Non-Readers by using the Project GRP (Guided Reading Procedure). It was quantitative-descriptive research conducted at Candelaria Elementary School-Main, specifically within the Grade 3 Faith learners, using a purposive sampling technique. The study aimed to assess the impact of the Guided Reading Procedure on non-reader learners and how it affected the classroom's standing in the reading program. To gather data in the acceptability level, a survey-questionnaire (self-made) was used, and data was collected in March 2023 using Google Forms. The data was presented in tabular form and analyzed using the Likert Scale. A conference with the parents and guardians of the non-reader learners was conducted, which resulted in a memorandum of understanding regarding the implementation of the program. This suggests that there was a collaborative effort to support the learners in their reading journey. The results showed progress among the non-reader learners through everyday reading monitoring and progress checks. However, the study faced challenges with absenteeism among the participants, which hindered the full implementation of the program. Despite this issue, seven learners managed to complete the program and demonstrated progress in their reading level, transitioning from non-readers to slow readers. This indicates that using a suitable reading material or program can be effective in improving the reading level of learners. In summary, the study showcased the positive impact of the Guided Reading Procedure in improving reading level among Grade Three Faith Non-Readers. It also highlighted the importance of addressing absenteeism to ensure the successful implementation of such reading interventions.

Keywords: *Guided-Reading Procedure, Non-readers, absenteeism*

INTRODUCTION

The global pandemic brought deprivation to learners' opportunity to develop their reading comprehension skills. The lack of support and guidance from home; and teacher-presence in the reading program, and access to internet during the two-year battle hindered the reading progress.

The future success of children lies in the ability to read fluently and understand what is read. Studies show that at least one out of five students significantly have difficulty in reading acquisition (Therrien, 2004). It can now be inferred that difficulty and the child's struggle in reading, to some extent, is an indication of an underlying learning disability. Basically, the problems are related to several varying factors exclusively related to reading. Usually, learners are not phonemically aware, failing to grasp the alphabetic principle and then applying these skills in a rapid and fluent manner and somehow relate reading to their own simple experiences (Belbes et al, 2022).

According to Mays (2008), many minority children are labeled as "at-risk," "developmentally delayed," and "not ready to learn" according to academic achievement in U.S. public schools today. As the minority population in the United States continues to grow, the rapidly increasing epidemic of students left behind academically is a concern for early childhood educators nationwide. According to Carter (2008), the term "at-risk" primarily refers to those students from families and communities with limited resources and correspondingly low educational outcomes. That is, at-risk students are those who are most likely to fail or drop out of school due to the challenges of poverty, broken homes, violence, limited English language proficiency, and other disadvantages in their family and community contexts. Furthermore, because the associations among race, ethnicity, and low academic performance and/or school failure are positive, the term "at risk" has become increasingly code or synonymous with low-income (or poor) and racial and ethnic minority students. Additionally, although "at risk" mainly pertains to class, ethnicity, gender, language skills, race, and academic achievement; however, many other classifications of students could be assigned to the at-risk category such as alcohol- and drug-dependent youth; physically and learning-disabled students; rural students; and students with mental health conditions.

With this matter, learners with problem in the phonemic awareness cause numerous non-readers to be remediate right away. The result of this study will help both the learners and the school to have zero non-readers, at the very least lessen its number. Reading is core to academic progress, because it underpins content-area learning in all subjects.

Researcher Küçükoğlu (2013), has found that teaching reading strategies is a key element in developing student comprehension. However, many teachers lack a solid foundation for teaching these reading comprehension strategies. Therefore, teachers need to be prepared on how to design effective comprehension strategies and how to

teach these strategies to their students. Therefore, this study aims to study the effective reading strategies in order to improve reading skills in language classes.

Upon coping up with the pandemic situation, schools give way to focus on the reading skills of the learners through various reading program, interventions, and remediations. Despite of the efforts, still a high number of non-readers were reported among grade three learners especially in the Grade Three Faith Section.

In the study of Davis et al, (2016), stated that adjustment means the act or process of changing or adjusting something or the cognitive flexibility of the teacher to respond to non-readers.

Strategies are high level plan to achieve one or more goals under conditions of uncertainty or simply the skill of making or carrying out plans to achieve a goal.

Students needed to be trained or guided on the use of different reading strategies so that they would know how to apply these strategies for successful comprehension of academic materials. Teachers will require the skills in order to teach reading strategies that will assist learners in understanding and applying the appropriate strategies to become skilled readers.

Scaffolds refer to the temporary support that the teacher uses to help the learners reach higher levels of comprehension and skill acquisition that they would not be able to achieve without assistance. Scaffolding refers to a variety of instructional techniques, which are used to move students progressively toward better understanding and, ultimately, greater independence in the learning process. This study endeavors to help novice reading teachers adjust their strategies in teaching nonreaders.

According to Adapon and Mangila (2020) education in the Philippines is hindered by poverty, technology, and lack of motivation and inspiration, especially reading education. Despite the socio-economic status, many Filipinos are unable to learn. Some families don't have enough money to send their kids to school; thus, kids grow up without being able to read and write. Some families are marginally fortunate that they can send their children to a public school; however, their children are learning basic reading at a plodding pace as there are not enough teachers and up-to-date reading materials in this school.

Remedial reading program has been established for a long time in Philippine basic education system. As a matter of fact, Genero's study (as cited in Gatcho & Bautista, 2019) disclosed how elementary and secondary schools of the country established their remedial reading programs to aid struggling readers. Principals should encourage their teachers to evaluate their learners' reading levels so they could provide appropriate interventions for them. Even though remediation among struggling readers has been practiced for several decades, it has reached its optimum only through the Department of Education (DepEd) Order 45, series of 2002 – Reading Literacy Program in the Elementary Schools.

According to Kennedy (2010), provision of a multifaceted professional development program for teachers is essential in addressing underachievement in literacy. When professional development is customized rather than pre-packaged, takes place over an extended period of time, and supports use of a range of research-based approaches (including a strong, ongoing focus on student achievement), it can have a major impact on student achievement, motivation, and engagement. Additionally, it is important that teacher creativity and individuality is honored throughout the professional development. Teachers in the study valued the opportunity to design a literacy program that aligned with the research base, responded to the needs of students, and provided autonomy for them to respond in unique and personal ways to the pedagogical content strategies they had learned. A systematic, coherent, integrated, and cognitively challenging curriculum is especially important in a high-poverty context. The design of the balanced literacy framework allowed for the development of students' creativity and agency, capitalized on their interests, and offered them choice and control over activities.

Parental involvement is another important factor in encouraging literacy and building proficient readers. Parental involvement in children's education has long been believed to promote a range of academic outcomes, including higher achievement, greater engagement in schoolwork, and lower dropout rates (Park & Holloway, 2017).

Guided Reading is a school-based intervention to improve the literacy achievement in students. All students benefit when teachers use the Guided Reading instructional model. Guided Reading is a component of a balanced literacy program providing differentiated, small-group reading instruction to four to six students with similar strengths and instructional needs or to heterogeneously grouped students. This approach to reading instruction provides teachers the opportunity to explicitly teach children the skills and comprehension strategies students need, thus facilitating the acquisition of reading proficiency. Some of the benefits of using the Guided Reading instructional model include individualized instruction, the use of books at students' reading levels, the opportunity to create and sustain meaning, the exposure to language that is context embedded, the structured format of the lesson, and the systematic evaluation of students' progress (Avalos, Plasencia, Chavez, & Rascon, 2007).

Likewise, this study is also beneficial to them in strategic management, when they employ effective learning in the classroom. Thus, this study provides new perspectives in seeing teachers' needs in teaching nonreaders more effectively.

Research Questions

This research aimed to develop the reading level of Grade Three Faith non-readers through Project GRP (Guided Reading Procedure).

Specifically, it sought to answer the following:

1. What is the reading level of grade three non-reader pupils during pre-test?
2. What is the reading level of grade three non-reader pupils during post-test?
3. Is there any significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results of grade three non-readers in reading level?

4. What is the acceptability level of Project GRP in terms of:
 - A. Teacher-Respondents
 - a. Content
 - b. Presentation
 - c. Appropriateness in target users
 - B. Learner-Respondents
 - a. Content
 - b. Presentation
 - c. Appropriateness in target users

Hypothesis:

There is no significant difference in the MPS pre-test and post-test results of Grade Three Non-readers in reading level using Project GRP.

METHODOLOGY

A. Participants and/or other Sources of Data and Information

The study involved seven selected learners from Grade III-Faith of Candelaria Elementary School – Main for SY 2022-2023 who were identified as non-readers. The reading intervention was facilitated by the researcher himself and lasted for the whole quarter.

Furthermore, Primary Teachers were also involved in the study to validate the reading materials used in Project GRP. Their role was likely to review and ensure the appropriateness and effectiveness of the materials in helping the non-reader learners enhance their reading skills.

The use of purposive sampling technique indicates that the researcher deliberately selected the participants based on specific criteria, in this case, non-readers from Grade III-Faith. This approach allowed the researcher to focus on the target group most in need of reading intervention.

With these details, it's evident that the study had a well-defined approach to address the reading difficulties of non-reader learners. The combination of Project GRP and the involvement of primary teachers for material validation, contributed to the positive progress observed in the seven participating non-reader learners.

B. Data Gathering Methods

The data collection followed a systematic timeline to assess the effectiveness of the reading intervention (Project GRP) and validate the reading materials used.

Upon crafting the Project GRP reading material and the pre-test, it was validated by the primary teachers; and the result were gathered, collected, analyzed, and tabulated. Before implementing the reading intervention (Project GRP), a pre-test

was conducted. This pre-assessment likely measured the baseline reading level of the seven selected non-reader learners. It aimed to establish their starting point before receiving any intervention. After the pre-assessment, the reading intervention was facilitated by the researcher. During this period, the non-reader pupils received targeted instruction and support to improve their reading skills. Following the completion of the intervention, a post-test was conducted to measure the reading level of the non-reader pupils after they had received the intervention. This post-assessment allowed the researcher to evaluate the impact of Project GRP on the participants' reading level.

In parallel with the implementation of Project GRP, the primary teachers were involved in validating the reading materials used in the intervention. The validity of the materials was assessed to ensure that they were appropriate, effective, and aligned with the objectives of the study. The results of both the pre-assessment and post-assessment, as well as the findings from the material validity measurement, were gathered and tabulated. The data were then analyzed to determine the effectiveness of the reading intervention and the validity of the materials used.

By following this timeline and systematically collected and analyzed data, the study can provide valuable insights into the impact of Project GRP on developing the reading level of Grade III-Faith non-reader learners. It also ensured that the reading material used was reliable and valid for the target audience.

C. Data Analysis

It is evident that the researcher employed a quantitative-descriptive research approach. Specifically, a pre-experimental design was utilized to investigate the significant difference between the pre- and post-assessment results of 3rd grade pupils' reading level. Instead, the researcher focused on measuring the changes in the reading level of the seven selected 3rd grade learners before and after the intervention. By comparing the pre-assessment and post-assessment results, the researcher aimed to determine if there was a significant improvement in the learners' reading level as a result of the intervention. The study's quantitative nature allows for the use of statistical analyses to assess the significance of the differences observed in the pre- and post-assessment results, providing more objective evidence of the intervention's impact on the learners' reading level.

To determine the reading level of the respondents, the researcher adopted the computation of the Phil-IRI Reading Level.

Using the result of the pre- and post-test assessment, dependent t-test was used to analyze the significant difference of the two assessments.

For the validity of the material, weighted mean was used to determine its level of acceptability in terms of content, presentation, and appropriateness to target user.

Paired samples dependent t-test is used to accept the null hypothesis. Impression at 0.05 level of significance for one-tailed since the study used the same group of pupils on both pre- and post-reading assessment.

Data were gathered, tabulated, and analyzed accordingly. Tabular method was used in the presentation of numerical data and validity of the material.

RESULTS

Table 1

Reading Level of the Grade Three Faith during Pre-Test

Learners' Name	# of Miscues	Word Reading Level	# Words in the Pre-Test	Reading Level
Learner 1	45	49.438	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 2	39	56.180	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 3	55	38.202	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 4	29	67.416	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 5	47	47.191	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 6	18	79.775	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 7	21	76.404	89	FRUSTRATION

Table 2

Reading Level of the Grade Three Faith during Post-Test

Learners' Name	# of Miscues	Word Reading Level	# Words in the Pre-Test	Reading Level
Learner 1	11	87.640	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 2	25	71.910	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 3	32	64.045	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 4	18	79.775	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 5	33	62.921	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 6	15	83.146	89	FRUSTRATION
Learner 7	17	80.899	89	FRUSTRATION

Table 3

Comparison of the Pre-Test and Post-Test Mean Scores of the Respondents after Using the Material

	MEAN	SD	MEAN DIFFERENCE	DIFFERENCE	COMPUTED VALUE	TABULAR VALUE	INTERPRETATION
PRE-TEST	11.714	2.119					
POST-TEST	26.143	5.986	14.429	0	6.975	2.00	SIGNIFICANT

Table 4.1.1

Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in Terms of Content (Teacher-respondents)

STATEMENTS	4	f	3	f	2	f	1	f	WEIGHTED MEAN	REMARKS
1. Contains ideas and concepts that are well-expressed in the material.	17	68	13	39	0	0	0	0	3.567	Highly Acceptable
2. Provides sufficient learning/information through appropriate examples in the reading lesson.	15	60	15	45	0	0	0	0	3.500	Acceptable
3. Gives different techniques and concrete concepts about the lessons in reading.	14	56	16	48	0	0	0	0	3.467	Acceptable
4. Provides appropriate sequences and concrete ideas for better understanding of the reading lesson.	19	76	11	33	0	0	0	0	3.633	Highly Acceptable
5. Provides aid for beginning readers.	18	72	12	36	0	0	0	0	3.600	Highly Acceptable
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN									3.553	Highly Acceptable

Table 4.1.2

Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in Terms of Presentation (Teacher-respondents)

STATEMENTS	4	f	3	f	2	f	1	f	WEIGHTED MEAN	REMARKS
1. Has organized and systematically arranged concepts.	16	64	10	30	4	8	0	0	3.400	Acceptable
2. Presents consistency in the lesson with reading-habit.	17	68	13	39	0	0	0	0	3.567	Highly Acceptable
3. Is attractive, reliable and easy to understand which provides ample experiences to the learners.	19	76	11	33	0	0	0	0	3.633	Highly Acceptable

4. The material has adequate margins, legible, type font and comfortable type-sized.	15	60	15	45	0	0	0	0	3.500	Acceptable
5. The layouts and graphics in the materials are attractive.	18	72	12	36	0	0	0	0	3.600	Highly Acceptable
6. Presents a lesson with originality suited for the learner for studying.	16	64	14	42	0	0	0	0	3.533	Highly Acceptable
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN									3.539	Highly Acceptable

Table 4.1.3

Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in Terms of Appropriateness in the Target Users (Teacher-respondents)

STATEMENTS	4	f	3	f	2	f	1	f	WEIGHTED MEAN	REMARKS
1. The lessons are well-arranged to provide clear sequence for understanding.	15	60	15	45	0	0	0	0	3.500	Acceptable
2. The material is appropriate to the age, maturity, and experience of the learners.	18	72	12	36	0	0	0	0	3.600	Highly Acceptable
3. The ideas and concepts are well-expressed in the reading material.	17	68	13	39	0	0	0	0	3.567	Highly Acceptable
4. The material gives the lessons and values to be earned by the learners.	16	64	14	42	0	0	0	0	3.533	Highly Acceptable
5. The contents of the material gives itself moral lessons and values to be learned by the learners.	15	60	15	45	0	0	0	0	3.500	Acceptable
6. Serves as the new instructional/reference reading material for beginning reading.	16	64	10	30	4	8	0	0	3.400	Acceptable
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN									3.517	Highly Acceptable

Table 4.2.1

Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in Terms of Content (Pupil-respondents)

STATEMENTS	4	f	3	f	2	f	1	f	WEIGHTED MEAN	REMARKS
1. Contains ideas and concepts that are well-expressed in the material. <i>(Naglalaman ng mga ideya at konsepto na mahusay na ipinahayag sa materyal.)</i>	4	16	3	9	0	0	0	0	3.571	Highly Acceptable
2. Provides sufficient learning/information through appropriate examples in the reading lesson. <i>(Nakapagbibigay ng sapat na pagkatuto o impormasyon sa pamamagitan ng mga angkop na halimbawa sa aralin sa pagbasa.)</i>	5	20	2	6	0	0	0	0	3.714	Highly Acceptable
3. Gives different techniques and concrete concepts about the lessons in reading. <i>(Nakapagbibigay ng iba't ibang teknik at konkretong konsepto tungkol sa mga aralin sa pagbasa.)</i>	6	24	1	3	0	0	0	0	3.857	Highly Acceptable
4. Provides appropriate sequences and concrete ideas for better understanding of the reading lesson. <i>(Nagbibigay ng angkop na pagkakasunod-sunod at konkretong ideya para sa higit na pag-unawa sa aralin sa pagbasa.)</i>	7	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.000	Highly Acceptable
5. Provides aid for beginning readers. <i>(Nagbibigay ng tulong para sa mga nagsisimulang mambabasa.)</i>	7	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.000	Highly Acceptable

AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN

3.829

**Highly
Acceptable**

Table 4.2.2

Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in Terms of Presentation (Pupil-respondents)

STATEMENTS	4	f	3	f	2	f	1	f	WEIGHTED MEAN	REMARKS
1. Has organized and systematically arranged concepts. <i>(May organisado at sistematikong pagkakaayos ng mga konsepto.)</i>	5	20	2	6	0	0	0	0	3.714	Highly Acceptable
2. Presents consistency in the lesson with reading-habit. <i>(Nakapaglalahad ng pagkakapare-pareho sa aralin na may ugali sa pagbasa.)</i>	4	16	2	6	1	2	0	0	3.429	Acceptable
3. Is attractive, reliable and easy to understand which provides ample experiences to the learners. <i>(May kaakit-akit, maaasahan at madaling maunawaan na nagbibigay ng sapat na karanasan sa mga mag-aaral.)</i>	6	24	1	3	0	0	0	0	3.857	Highly Acceptable
4. The material has adequate margins, legible, type font and comfortable type-sized. <i>(Ang materyal ay may sapat na mga margin, nababasa, uri ng font at komportableng laki ng uri.)</i>	5	20	1	3	1	2	0	0	3.571	Highly Acceptable
5. The layouts and graphics in the materials are attractive. <i>(Ang mga layout at graphics sa mga materyales ay kaakit-akit.)</i>	6	24	1	3	0	0	0	0	3.857	Highly Acceptable

6. Presents a lesson with originality suited for the learner for studying.
(Naglalahad ng isang aralin na may orihinalidad na angkop para sa mag-aaral para sa pag-aaral.)

5	20	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	3.714	Highly Acceptable
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN									3.690	Highly Acceptable

Table 4.2.3

Weighted Mean Distribution of the Perceived Level of Acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in Terms of Appropriateness in the Target Users (Pupil-respondents)

STATEMENTS	4	f	3	f	2	f	1	f	WEIGHTED MEAN	REMARKS
1. The lessons are well-arranged to provide clear sequence for understanding.	5	20	2	6	0	0	0	0	3.714	Highly Acceptable
2. The material is appropriate to the age, maturity, and experience of the learners.	6	24	1	3	0	0	0	0	3.857	Highly Acceptable
3. The ideas and concepts are well-expressed in the reading material.	5	20	2	6	0	0	0	0	3.714	Highly Acceptable
4. The material gives the lessons and values to be earned by the learners.	7	28	0	0	0	0	0	0	4.000	Highly Acceptable
5. The contents of the material gives itself moral lessons and values to be learned by the learners.	6	24	1	3	0	0	0	0	3.857	Highly Acceptable
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN									3.829	Highly Acceptable

DISCUSSION

Table 1 showed that all of the respondents fall under the Frustration Reading Level during the Pre-test Assessment. Learner 6 has the least number of misread words during the pre-test while Learners 1, 3, and 5 got the highest number of misread with 45, 55, and 47 respectively.

Table 2 showed that the respondents were fall under the Frustration Reading Level after using the validated Project GRP reading material. On the other hand, the respondents were remained in the Frustration Reading Level after using the reading material. Hence, it showed a drop down in the number of miscues and increase their word reading level.

Table 3 presents the summary of values for testing the significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents.

Among the seven respondents, the mean of the obtained pre-test scores is 11.714 with a standard deviation of 2.119 and the mean of the post-test scores is 26.143 with a standard deviation of 5.986, respectively resulting to a mean difference of 14.429.

There is a notable difference in the standard deviation of pre- and post-test. The standard deviation of post-test is higher than of the pre-test. When subjected to t-test, it garnered a t-value of 6.975 which is higher than the tabular value of 2.00 at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is a significant difference between the scores of the learners in the pre- and post-test before and after the use of the Project GRP reading material is approved.

Table 4.1.1 shows the weighted mean distribution of the perceived level of acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in terms of content. The evaluators evaluated the content with five statements with the following weighted mean – statement 1 got 3.567, statement 2 got 3.500, statement 3 had 3.467, statement 4 received 3.633 and statement 5 got 3.600 with a remark of highly acceptable (statements 1, 4 and 5) and acceptable for statements 2 and 3.

Over-all, the Project GRP Reading Material in terms of content got an average weighted mean of 3.553 that falls on highly acceptable remark.

Poor reading level among children and youth is an ongoing concern. Data show stagnant performance in reading achievement over the past decades only about one-third of fourth-graders exhibiting proficient reading skills (Snyder, De Brey, & Dillow, 2016). Low reading achievement is associated with adversities in several areas, including educational progress, employment opportunities, and health outcomes (Ritchie & Bates, 2013).

Absolutely, teaching reading strategies to students is crucial for their successful comprehension of academic materials. When students are trained or guided in using different reading strategies, they become equipped with the necessary tools to understand and engage with various texts effectively.

Teachers play a vital role in this process as they need to be skilled in teaching these reading strategies effectively. Professional development and ongoing training for teachers are essential to equip them with the necessary skills and knowledge to instruct students in reading strategies. Teachers should model the use of these strategies and provide ample opportunities for students to practice and apply them independently.

By integrating reading strategies instruction into the curriculum, educators can foster a classroom environment where students become skilled readers capable of comprehending and analyzing a wide range of academic materials. This, in turn, will have a positive impact on their overall academic performance and success.

Table 4.1.2 shows the weighted mean distribution of the perceived level of acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in terms of presentation. The evaluators evaluated the presentation with six statements with the following weighted mean – statement 1 got 3.400, statement 2 got 3.567, statement 3 had 3.633, statement 4 received 3.500, statement 5 got 3.600 and statement 6 got 3.533 with a remark of highly acceptable (statements 2, 3, 5 and 6) and acceptable for statements 1 and 4. Over-all, the Project GRP Reading Material in terms of presentation got an average weighted mean of 3.539 that falls on highly acceptable remark.

There are lots of strategies for improving the reading skills of a learner. As cited in Pourhosein & Sabouri (2016), the following are some of the effective ways: activating and using background knowledge; generating and asking questions; making inferences; predicting; summarizing; visualizing; and comprehension monitoring.

In response to the pupils' poor reading skills, the Department of Education issued DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s. 2019 to make every learner a proficient reader where schools across the country are tasked to develop their reading skills. There is a need to strengthen every learner's reading proficiency and nurture a culture of reading, which is a requisite skill in all content areas (Cabalo & Cabalo, 2019).

As important as foundational word-reading and bridging skills are to reading comprehension, research has shown that they are not sufficient for strong comprehension. For example, just because a reader can fluently read the words in "Not Just a Hole in the Ground" does not mean that the reader will glean from the article the characteristics of summer and winter woodchuck burrows. That understanding requires a broader range of knowledge, strategies, and dispositions (Duke, Ward, & Pearson, 2021).

Consistency in providing suitable reading materials is crucial in supporting learners' optimal learning and development, allowing them to progress at their own pace. Here are some reasons why consistency in reading materials is beneficial for learners.

Consistent reading materials ensure that learners receive a continuous and structured learning experience. This continuity helps build upon previously acquired knowledge and skills, fostering a deeper understanding of concepts over time. Regular exposure to consistent reading materials allows learners to practice and build fluency in reading. Familiarity with the format and content of the materials enables them to read with greater ease and speed. Consistency creates a sense of comfort and confidence in learners. When they know what to expect from the reading materials, they are more willing to engage with them and take ownership of their learning.

Providing consistent reading materials tailored to learners' needs and interests allows for personalized learning experiences. Learners can focus on topics and themes that resonate with them, which enhances their motivation and engagement. Repeated exposure to key concepts and vocabulary in consistent reading materials reinforces learning and aids in long-term retention. Consistency does not mean a one-size-fits-all approach. Educators can use a consistent framework while differentiating reading materials to accommodate learners' diverse needs and abilities. Using consistent reading materials makes it easier for educators to monitor learners' progress effectively. They can assess how learners are mastering concepts and skills over time. Consistent exposure to reading materials encourages learners to develop regular reading habits. As they become accustomed to engaging with reading materials, they are more likely to pursue independent reading beyond the classroom.

Consistency allows educators to scaffold learning appropriately, gradually introducing more complex reading materials as learners advance their skills. Consistent reading materials streamline lesson planning for educators, allowing them to focus on instructional strategies and differentiation rather than constantly seeking new materials.

By maintaining consistency in the selection of reading materials, educators can create a stable and supportive learning environment that empowers learners to explore, grow, and succeed in their reading journey at their own pace. This approach fosters love for reading and lifelong learning in students, which is essential for their academic and personal development.

Table 4.1.3 shows the weighted mean distribution of the perceived level of acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in terms of appropriateness to the target users. The evaluators evaluated the presentation with six statements with the following weighted mean – statement 1 got 3.500, statement 2 got 3.600, statement 3 had 3.567, statement 4 received 3.533, statement 5 got 3.500 and statement 6 got 3.400 with a remark of highly acceptable (statements 2, 3 and 4) and acceptable for statements 1, 5 and 6. Over-all, the Project GRP Reading Material in terms of appropriateness to the target users got an average weighted mean of 3.517 that falls on highly acceptable remark.

In considering the science of reading, many researchers cite the National Reading Panel's (National Institute of Child Health and Human Development, 2000) review and analysis of research related to reading instruction, which identified five key concepts in

reading: phonemic awareness, phonics, fluency, vocabulary, and comprehension. Although these “big five” are certainly important, and each has received attention in this piece, they do not represent an exhaustive list of contributors to reading that teachers should consider when designing literacy instruction. Scientific research has shown that motivation for reading is another important determinant of reading comprehension; one that we ignore at our peril.

Absolutely, presenting suited reading materials is essential in helping learners acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. When reading materials are appropriately selected, they cater to the learners' current level of comprehension, interests, and learning needs. This alignment ensures that learners can effectively engage with the material, which enhances their learning experience and outcomes.

When learners find the reading materials interesting and relevant to their lives, they are more likely to be motivated to read and learn from them. This engagement fosters a positive attitude towards reading and learning. Reading materials that match the learners' current reading abilities and background knowledge increase the chances of successful comprehension. Learners are more likely to understand and retain the information presented.

Suited reading materials allow learners to practice and apply the reading strategies they have been taught. This practice helps them develop their reading skills further. Success in comprehending suited reading materials boosts learners' confidence in their reading abilities. This confidence encourages them to tackle more challenging texts in the future. Providing reading materials that reflect the learners' culture, experiences, and backgrounds validates their identities and creates a more inclusive learning environment. Suited reading materials allow educators to differentiate instruction, catering to the diverse needs and abilities of individual learners within the classroom.

When learners can read and understand materials on their own, they become more independent learners, able to explore and acquire knowledge beyond the classroom setting. It is essential for educators to consider learners' proficiency levels, interests, and learning goals when selecting reading materials. This may involve using various texts, including fiction, non-fiction, poetry, and digital resources. Regularly assessing learners' progress and adjusting the materials accordingly ensure that they continue to receive appropriately suited content as they advance in their reading abilities.

Ultimately, providing suited reading materials is a foundational aspect of effective reading instruction, contributing significantly to learners' overall academic growth and lifelong learning journey.

Table 4.2.1 shows the weighted mean distribution of the perceived level of acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in terms of content. The pupil-respondents evaluated the content with the following weighted mean of 3.571, 3.714, 3.857, 4.000 and 4.000 respectively from the statements 1 to 5 with highly acceptable remarks on all the statements.

All five statements received weighted mean scores indicating "highly acceptable" levels of perceived acceptability from the pupil-respondents. Specifically, statements 4 and 5 garnered the highest ratings with a weighted mean of 4.000, suggesting strong approval and satisfaction regarding certain aspects or criteria of the reading material's content.

Based on the pupil-respondent's evaluations, this average weighted mean of 3.829 falls within the "highly acceptable" range. This indicates that, collectively, the respondents view the content of the Project GRP Reading Material favorably, highlighting its quality, relevance, and effectiveness in meeting their instructional or learning needs.

In summary, the findings underscore a positive perception among pupil-respondents regarding the content of the Project GRP Reading Material. The consistently high weighted mean scores across all statements reflect a consensus of "high acceptability," affirming the material's overall quality and suitability from the perspective of those directly engaging with it.

Table 4.2.2 shows the weighted mean distribution of the perceived level of acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in terms of presentation. Statements 1, 3, 4, 5, and 6 received weighted mean scores indicating a "highly acceptable" level of perceived acceptability from the pupil-respondents. Specifically, these statements reflect strong approval and satisfaction concerning various aspects or criteria related to the presentation of the reading material. Statement 2 garnered a weighted mean score of 3.429, falling within the "acceptable" range. While this statement meets the basic acceptability criteria, it may suggest areas for potential improvement or refinement in the presentation aspect evaluated.

Considering the collective evaluations across all statements, the Project GRP Reading Material achieved an average weighted mean score of 3.690 in terms of presentation. The cumulative weighted mean of 3.690 positions the reading material within the "highly acceptable" category. This indicates a favorable perception among pupil-respondents regarding the overall quality, effectiveness, and appeal of the reading material's presentation.

In summary, the findings from Table 4.2.2 highlight a predominantly positive perception among pupil-respondents concerning the presentation of the Project GRP Reading Material. While most statements received ratings of "highly acceptable," the material demonstrates strong alignment with respondents' expectations and needs. However, targeted attention to areas with "acceptable" ratings could further enhance the presentation's effectiveness and overall acceptability among users.

Table 4.2.3 shows the weighted mean distribution of the perceived level of acceptability of the Project GRP Reading Material in terms of appropriateness to the target users. The pupil-respondents evaluated the presentation with five statements with the following weighted mean – statement 1 and 3 got 3.714, statement 2 and 5 got 3.857, while statement 4 received 4.000.

The majority of the statements, specifically statements 1, 3, 4, and 5, received weighted mean scores indicating a "highly acceptable" level of perceived appropriateness for the target users. These ratings suggest that the respondents find these aspects of the reading material well-suited, relevant, and aligned with the needs and preferences of the intended audience.

Statement 4 stands out with a weighted mean score of 4.000, indicating an exceptionally high level of appropriateness as perceived by the pupil-respondents. This suggests that this particular aspect or criterion of the reading material resonates strongly with the target users, meeting or exceeding their expectations and requirements.

Aggregating the evaluations across all statements, the Project GRP Reading Material achieved an average weighted mean score of 3.829 concerning its appropriateness to the target users. With an average weighted mean of 3.829, the reading material falls within the "highly acceptable" category regarding its appropriateness for the intended users. This indicates a strong alignment between the material's design, content, and presentation and the preferences, needs, and expectations of the target audience, as perceived by the pupil-respondents.

In summary, Table 4.2.3's findings underscore a predominantly positive perception among pupil-respondents regarding the Project GRP Reading Material's appropriateness for its target users. The consistently high weighted mean scores across most statements reflect a consensus of "high acceptability," highlighting the material's relevance, effectiveness, and suitability for its intended audience.

Conclusions

In light of this research, which aimed to develop the reading level of Grade Three Faith non-readers through Project GRP (Guided Reading Procedure), the following conclusions were made after the study.

1. The researcher used a suited reading material for the grade three non-readers addressing the learner's problem in reading skills. Though the result showed that majority of the learners tested were on the frustration level before and after using the Project GRP, it was evident that there was a progress in their reading skills. The lessen numbers of miscues before and after using the reading material were also marked as their progress.
2. There is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results of grade three non-readers in reading level.
3. The validated reading material made by the researcher were coherently addressed the gap in reading among the grade three non-readers. The continuation of the reading content from sounds to stories valued the reading habit among the respondents (both the teacher-validators and learner-validators) which showed the Tables 4.1.1 to 4.2.3 with a remark of highly acceptable.

Recommendations

To make the study more effective and authentic, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. To enhance the generalizability of the findings, increase the number of participants involved in the study. Include a control group that does not receive the Project GRP intervention. This will help the comparing the effectiveness of the information more accurately and ruling out the factors that might influence the learners' reading level.
 2. Provide professional development for teachers on the implementation of the Project GRP to ensure consistency and effectiveness in its delivery. The collection and analyzation feedback from teachers can strengthen the usability and impact of the reading materials and intervention. Also, the involve of the parents in the reading intervention process by providing them with strategies and resources to support their children's reading development at home. can influence reading practices on students' progress to understand the holistic impact of the intervention.
 3. Gather feedback from students about their experiences and perceptions of the reading intervention to identify areas for improvement and use these feedbacks to make iterative improvements to the Project GRP, ensuring that it remains responsive to the needs of the learners.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

DECLARATION OF ANTI-PLAGIARISM AND ABSENCE OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST

[Declaration of Anti-Plagiarism]

1. I/We, **DARWIN F. TABERNILLA**, understand that plagiarism is the act of taking and using another's ideas and works and passing them off as one's own. This includes explicitly copying the whole work of another person or that of the undersigned proponents and/or using some parts of their work without proper acknowledgment and referencing.
2. I/We hereby attest to the originality of this research proposal and have cited properly all the references used. I/We further commit that all deliverables and the completed research emanating from this proposal shall be of original content. I/We shall use appropriate citations in referencing other works from various sources. I/We also hereby attest that this research has not yet been finished and is not part of the researcher/s' thesis or dissertation.
3. I/We understand that violation of this declaration and commitment shall be subject to consequences and shall be dealt with accordingly by the Department of Education.

(Sgd.) DARWIN F. TABERNILLA

Signature Over Printed Name of Lead Researcher

02/12/2023

Date Signed

[Declaration of Absence of Conflict of Interest]

1. I/We, **DARWIN F. TABERNILLA**, understand that conflict of interest refers to situations in which financial or other personal considerations may compromise my/our judgment in evaluating, conducting, or reporting research.
2. I/We hereby declare that I/we do not have any personal conflict of interest that may arise from my/our submission of my/our research proposal. I/We understand that my/our research proposal may be returned to me/us if found out that there is a conflict of interest during the initial screening or review as per DO 16, s. 2017.
3. Further, in case of any form of conflict of interest (possible or actual) which may inadvertently emerge during the conduct of my/our research, I/we will duly report it to the research committee for immediate action.
4. I/we understand that I/we may be held accountable by the Department of Education for any conflict of interest which I/we have intentionally concealed.

(Sgd.) DARWIN F. TABERNILLA

Signature Over Printed Name of Lead Researcher

02/12/2023

Date Signed

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